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Marine Protected Areas Odyssey Lastovo Islands Nature Park (Croatia)

September 2023

Marine Protected Areas Odyssey – Report of the 2023 mission in the Lastovo Islands Nature Park (Croatia)

January 2024

FOREWORD

Context, fundings and partner: This study is part of the "MPA Odyssey in the Mediterranean Sea" program, developed by WWF-France and realised in partnership with Septentrion Environnement (SE). This report presents the actions undertaken and the results of the field mission of September 2023, carried out on the territory and with the partnership of the Lastovo Islands Nature Park (LINP). The partners associated with this mission are the WWF Adriatic. The project is co-funded thanks to the financial support of the Pew Bertarelli Ocean Legacy.

Program leader: Denis Ody (WWF-France)

Scientific leader: Adrien Cheminée (SE)

Scientific divers: Olivier Bianchimani (SE), Adrien Cheminée (SE), Justine Richaume (SE), Tristan Estaque (SE), Anouck Ody (SE), Sébastien Personnic (SE).

Blue Panda Crew (Seanergie) : Ernesto Izzo (Captain), Pauline Faugères (sailor), Lou Le Galliot (sailor), Hugo Pierre (sailor).

Data analysis and scientific writing: Tristan Estaque, Lucie Nunez and Adrien Cheminée

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1. Introduction

This study is part of the "MPA Odyssey in the Mediterranean" programme, directed by WWF-France. The MPA Odyssey is a multi-year scientific field expedition, carried out on board the *Blue Panda*, and aiming at reinforcing the level of protection within Mediterranean MPAs.

This report presents the actions carried out and the results of the September 2023 field mission carried out in and with the partnership of the Lastovo Islands Nature Park (LINP).

The main objective of this mission was to collect data *via* underwater visual census aimed at describing the state of ichthyological populations (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 1985) within the LINP: (1) Firstly that was done in order to assess the state of ichthyological populations in the LINP, with sampled sites located both inside and outside potential No-Take Zones (NTZ), along the entire coastline of the Park ; (2) Besides, these data were gathered as a "baseline" in order to characterise particular sites and/or those that are likely to be integrated into strong protection zones in the future ; Moreover, (3) we aimed to put these data into perspective with data from other MPAs in the Mediterranean (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008).

2. Conduct of the mission

The team consisted of 6 scientific divers who carried out the underwater visual census, a mission leader, and 4 crew members.

Scientific team

Olivier BIANCHIMANI – Septentrion Environnement – Diving organisation and safety supervision, scientific diver.

Adrien CHEMINÉE – Septentrion Environnement – Scientific supervision, scientific diver.

Justine RICHAUME – Septentrion Environnement – Scientific diver.

Tristan ESTAQUE – Septentrion Environnement – Scientific diver.

Denis ODY – WWF France – Mission leader, surface security, scientific diver.

Sébastien PERSONNIC – Septentrion Environnement – Scientific diver.

Anouck ODY – Septentrion Environnement – Scientific diver.

Blue Panda Team

Ernesto IZZO – Seanergie – Captain

Pauline FAUGÈRES – Seanergie – Sailor

Lou LE GALLIOT – Seanergie – Sailor

Hugo PIERRE – Seanergie – Sailor

3. Material and methods

3.1. Location and presentation of sampling areas and sites

Fifty one sites, located in four areas, were sampled during the mission (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Map of the different areas and sites sampled during the MPA Odyssey mission – Lastovo Islands Nature Park. Each site is represented by a dot and number. Blue polygons display potential No-Take Zones as foreseen in the current management plan (see method section).

The study sites (Fig. 1) were selected on the basis of available data concerning the description of biotopes and biocenoses and on the advice of local managers and scientists. Study sites were selected along the coastline and had to present habitats with the following characteristics: infralittoral rocky reef with few *Posidonia oceanica* cover (<50%) and located between 5 and 15 meters deep. We targeted this habitat since it is known to be a representative case study in order to quantify the response of fish assemblages to protection level (Garcia-Rubies and Zabala, 1990). Nevertheless, some variations in habitat characteristics still remained, and sometimes displayed shallower rocky bottoms (4-5 m) or areas mixed with a small percent cover of *Posidonia oceanica* meadow growing over the rocky bed. Sites and their characteristics are listed in Appendix A01 and in the result full database (available upon request).

Sites were *a priori* grouped into four areas that displayed homogeneity in terms of both geomorphological and fishing regulation characteristics: the western islands of Otok Susac, Bijelac, Kopist and Skoj od Kopist have been gathered into the “West Archipelago” area, the main island and the adjacent small islands of the LINP has been divided into 2 areas (“West Mainland” and “East Mainland”), while the eastern islands of Banci and Glavat has been gathered into the “East Archipelago” area (Fig. 1).

In all these areas, the biocenosis of the infralittoral rocky reef was characterised by varying degrees of arborescent macrophyte cover. At several sites, fairly dense algal forests of *Cystoseira* spp. (*sensu lato*) algae (*Cystoseira foeniculacea* f. *latiramosa* and *C. foeniculacea* f. *tenuiramosa*) and Sargassum (*Sargassum vulgare*) were present, providing a key habitat function for many of the fish species recorded during this study.

3.2. Protocols for underwater inventories

As regards the sampling method, we used underwater visual census (UVC) of fish assemblages, performed along 25 m long and 5 m wide belt-transects. Inside each sampling unit, abundances of all fish species were recorded, or estimated for large groups, and individual size was estimated in 2 cm increments (for individuals smaller than 30 cm), and 6 cm increments for larger ones (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008, 1985). Only one pass per transect was made, focusing on necto-benthic species (Sparidae, Labridae, Serranidae, etc.) (Harmelin, 1987), but excluding cryptic ones (Scorpaenidae), since necto-benthic ones are the most sensitive to the level of protection (Garcia-Rubies and Zabala, 1990).

In each site, sampling units (n = 6 transects, except in special cases) were carried out according to stratified random sampling, targeting the habitat described above, among an average depth range of 5 to 15 meters, and with a limited percentage of *P. oceanica* meadows cover (maximum of 50%, where possible).

3.3. Data Analysis

3.3.1. Fish assemblage descriptors

The data analysis was carried out using underwater visual observation data (fish abundances and sizes) acquired by scientific divers within **305 transects** conducted across **51 sites**, grouped into 4 areas. Six transects were carried out at each site, with the exception of site 22 where 5 transects were carried out due to a technical problem. Descriptive variables of fish assemblages extracted from raw data included species occurrence (proportion of transects where a species was present), overall dominance (proportion of individuals of a species in the total count of all species), total abundance, total biomass, species richness, relative abundance and relative biomass per species (i.e. population composition), and total length per species. Biomass was calculated from the abundance and size of individuals per species using commonly used size-biomass conversion factors for fishes dwelling in the infralittoral rocky reef biocenosis (Thibaut et al., 2017).

After examining species occurrence, the gregarious species (*Chromis chromis*, *Spicara* spp., *Boops boops*, and *Atherina* spp.), which were abundant on the majority of transects, were subsequently removed from the data to conduct further analyses without masking the signal of less abundant species. Among observed species (Appendix A2), Mediterranean species commonly targeted by fishing were also examined more closely. We used a standard list of targeted species for the Mediterranean which included *Dentex dentex*, *Diplodus annularis*, *D. puntazzo*, *D. sargus*, *D. vulgaris*, *Coris julis*, *Labrus merula*, *L. viridis*, *Mullus surmuletus*, *Oblada melanura*, *Serranus scriba*, *Sarpa salpa*, and *Sparus aurata*. The explanatory variables for the sampling design were the observation area (fixed factor with 4 modalities) and the observation site (nested factor within the area, with 51 modalities). We also calculated the -log ratio of abundance

divided by biomass. This descriptor allows checking whether, at constant abundance, fish are larger or smaller in an area. Differences in total abundance and total biomass between areas were statistically tested. Since the data did not have a normal distribution and the homogeneity of variances was not applicable, a Kruskal-Wallis test (a non-parametric test similar to Anova) was conducted. Pairwise differences between the various modalities of the "Area" factor were then tested using a post-hoc Siegel and Castellan test, adapted to the Kruskal-Wallis test.

On the other hand, an analysis of the ratio of total abundance inside NTZs (No-Take Zones) *versus* outside NTZs (ONTZs - Outside No-Take Zones) and of the biomass inside NTZs *versus* outside NTZs (ONTZs) allowed us to compare the effectiveness of protections in place in the marine protected areas studied under the BIOMEX project (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008) and those of the Odyssey of MPAs project. For the Lastovo Islands Nature Park, the abundance and biomass ratios were made between potential-NTZs and outside potential-NTZs. A comparison with the average ratios of respectively abundance and biomass between unprotected zones and NTZs found in other Mediterranean MPAs (Giakoumi et al., 2017) also helped to discuss the observed average in the studied MPA here.

All figures and descriptive/inferential statistics were generated using R Studio software v. 4.0.5 (R Core Team, 2017).

3.3.2. Scenarios of stronger protection

As an improvement of the current management plan and based on the MPA's Odyssey program results, we proposed alongside our field data analysis a new management scenario with the creation of larger No-Take Zones (NTZ) and Professional Fishing Reserved Areas (PFRA) (see Fig. 19 in the discussion), where recreational fishing is prohibited, and we compared the fish "Production" that would be expected for this scenario *versus* the current situation, for the same superficies.

If we consider for example a given zone, with a mean *in situ* biomass of fish, the "Production" is what is expected to be produced and exported annually per unit of surface (ha), through natural growth and reproduction of these fish individuals. The Production is directly and positively correlated with the "*in situ* Biomass": previous studies from the BIOMEX program (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008), obtained in 6 mediterranean model MPAs, demonstrated that the "Production/*in situ* Biomass" ratio is typically about 0.315 and 0.366 in average for sites located respectively inside or outside no-take zones. This ratio Production/*in situ* Biomass depends also on the proportion of the different categories of fish in the assemblage. Knowing the in-situ biomass of a given zone, and using these ratios, it is consequently possible to evaluate the production expected from this given zone under various scenarios : the difference of production between a scenario where the zone becomes a NTZ or remains in the current not-protected situation can be considered as the "revenues of a capital" and also as what is available for fishing around the NTZ.

The potential "*in situ* biomasses" of the new NTZ in the present scenario have been calculated with the *in situ* biomasses observed in this study multiplied by the average ratio of biomass inside/outside NTZs known from 24 mediterranean MPAs (Giakoumi et al., 2017). The value of this ratio is x2.3 and should be considered as rather conservative

since we had higher values in BIOMEX (x5.6 in average and up to x9.7) and in MPAs Odyssey data in Corsica in 2022 (x4.5; Estaque et al., 2023).

We performed the same calculation if designing a Professional Fishing Reserved Areas surrounding the NTZ (PFRA): we took into account the increase of “In situ Biomass” in this Professional Fishing Reserved Areas (PFRA) resulting from prohibiting recreational fishing. We used data from a similar design in Corsica (Estaque et al. 2023) where the in-situ biomasses in the PFRA are 2.7 and 3.7 times higher than in open areas. We used x2 as a conservative estimate.

In summary, we calculated estimates of :

- The **current production** of the entire zone before setting up any NTZ or PFRA;
- Its **potential production** increased by the exedentary production resulting from the setting up of the **NTZ** (i.e. production available around the NTZ once protected *versus* production available when not protected), while the rest of the zone remains open to all type of fishing ;
- Its **potential production** increased by the two exedentary productions resulting (a) from the setting up of the **NTZ** and (b) resulting from the setting up of the surrounding **PFRA**.

4. Results

4.1. Sampling and main quantitative properties of Teleost communities

4.1.1 Occurrence frequency and species richness

Including the gregarious species, *C. julis* was the most regularly observed species (occurring in 99% of transects), followed by *Thallasoma pavo* (96%), *Symphodus tinca* (90%) and *C. chromis* (88%) (Fig. 2). It is interesting to note that the thermophilic species *Sparisoma cretense* was also present in 68% of transects. *D. vulgaris* was the only species of its genus present in a majority of transects (64%).

In terms of dominance, excluding gregarious species, the most abundant species recorded was *C. julis* (Fig. 3), which represented more than 25% of all fish recorded. It was followed by *S. tinca* (22%), *T. pavo* (11%) and *D. vulgaris* (7%).

Figure 2. Occurrence frequency of species observed during the mission, on all transects, all sites combined (with gregarious species).

Figure 3. Global dominance of species observed during the mission, on all transects, all sites combined (excluding gregarious species).

Species richness per transect across all sites and areas was on average 11.5 taxa. Species richness per transect averaged by site (Fig. 4) varied from 7 taxa for site 23 (West Archipelago area) to 16 taxa for site 18 (West Archipelago area). Considering the average richness by area (i.e. cumulated richness per transect, averaged by area) (Fig. 5), the average species richness varied from 10 taxa for East Archipelago area to 12 for the West Archipelago and East Mainland areas.

Total species richness (i.e. all transects cumulated) per site varied from 14 taxa for site 29 (West Mainland area) to 27 taxa for site 48 (East Mainland area). Considering all areas, the total species richness was 41 taxa (Appendix A2), and ranged from 30 taxa for the East Archipelago area to 38 taxa for the East Mainland area.

Figure 4. Average species richness per transect by site (with gregarious species). Colors indicate the area to which the site belongs to and sites are classified in geographical order. The error bars (whiskers) correspond to the standard error, represented here only as a positive value (+S.E.) for a better display.

Figure 5. Species richness per transect, averaged per area, all sites combined (with gregarious species). Error bars correspond to the standard error (+/-).

4.1.2. Mean abundance

The total abundance of fish (excluding gregarious species) per transect averaged per site (Fig. 6) ranged from 29.3 ind.125 m⁻² for sites 12 (West Mainland area) to 210.0 ind.125 m⁻² for site 15 (West Mainland area). The overall average abundance across all sites (excluding gregarious species) was 76 ± 3 ind.125 m⁻². Sites 15 and 39 showed a significant average abundance of *S. tinca* (178 ind.125 m⁻² and 86 ind.125 m⁻², respectively). On these sites, numerous juveniles of this species were indeed recorded in the arborescent strata composed of *C. foeniculacea* and *S. vulgare* and colonizing the infralittoral rock. On site 45 we censused a high mean abundance of *D. vulgaris* (56 ind.125 m⁻²) and *S. salpa* (30.5 ind.125 m⁻²). It is interesting to note that the thermophile species *Sparisoma cretense* was observed on a lot of sites with a mean abundance ranging from 0.17 ind.125 m⁻² in site 34 and site 29 up to 8.7 ind.125 m⁻² in site 18. On many sites we also observed individuals of *Scorpaena maderensis*, which is also a thermophile species.

Figure 6. Mean abundance (ind.125 m⁻²) per site. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (+/- S.E.).

The total abundance per transect averaged per area (Fig. 7) varied significantly between areas (Kruskal-Wallis test, $\text{Chi}^2 = 18.873$, $p = 1.8\text{e-}4$), ranging from 63.2 ind.125 m⁻² for the West Mainland Area to 88.0 ind.125 m⁻² for the East Mainland area. The West Mainland area showed a significantly lower mean abundance per transect in comparison to all the other areas (Siegel and Castellan post-hoc test, $p \leq 0.05$). The three other areas (West Archipelago, East Mainland and East Archipelago) showed comparable mean abundance per transect and no significant differences were observed (Siegel and Castellan post-hoc test, $p \geq 0.05$).

The East Archipelago, West Archipelago and East mainland areas showed a high mean abundance of *C. julis* (25 ind.125 m⁻², 22 ind.125 m⁻² and 20 ind.125 m⁻², respectively). A high mean abundance of *S. tinca* has been observed in each area, especially in the West Mainland area where the mean observed abundance of this species was 21 ind.125 m⁻². The area with the highest abundance of a *Diplodus* genus species was the East Mainland where the mean abundance of *D. vulgaris* was 9 ind.125 m⁻².

Figure 7. Mean total abundance per transect (ind./125 m⁻²) by area. Whiskers correspond to the standard error (+/- S.E.). Letters illustrate the significance or non-significance of differences in mean given by statistical tests; two areas with no letters in common differ significantly from each other for the considered response variable.

4.1.3. Mean Total Length (TL)

Overall, for each species of the Teleost assemblage surveyed, the mean lengths (TL: Total Length) of the individuals were fairly similar between the different zones (Fig. 8). The fish species targeted by the fishery were not on average larger in any particular area. Moreover, the mean length of the individuals observed was quite small overall, particularly for individuals of the *Diplodus* genus (see references in discussion section). Nevertheless, it can be noted that *S. tinca* individuals were on average smaller in the West Mainland area and that *T. pavo* individuals were on average smaller in the East Archipelago area.

Figure 8. Description of the observed Teleost assemblage (excluding gregarious species) in terms of mean individual size (TL: Total Length, in cm) by observation area. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (-E.S.).

4.1.4. Biomass

The mean biomass for all transects combined was $2954 \pm 326 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$ gregarious species included, and $2445 \pm 290 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$ when not considering gregarious species. The mean total biomass per site (Fig. 9) varied from $730 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$ for site 16 (West Archipelago area) to $17753 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$ for site 19 (West Archipelago area). Within the East Mainland area, sites 9, 41, 45 and 48 showed a mean biomass of over $4000 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$.

Some sites contrasted with others in terms of mean biomass of certain species. On site 19 (West Archipelago area) we recorded a shoal of 30 *Dentex dentex* with a total length of 55 cm resulting in a mean biomass of $11638 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$. The site 48 (East Mainland area) showed a high mean biomass of $4778 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$ of *O. melanura*. Sites 45 (East Mainland area) and 19 (West Archipelago area) showed the highest mean biomass recorded for *D. vulgaris* with $2154 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$ and $1543 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$ respectively.

At the area level (Fig. 10) the mean total biomass varied significantly between areas (Kruskal-Wallis test, $\text{Chi}^2 = 13.402$, $p = 3.8e-4$) and ranged from $1599 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$ for the West Mainland area to $3315 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$ for the West Archipelago area. The West Mainland area showed a significantly lower mean biomass per transect than the West Archipelago and the East Mainland areas (Siegel and Castellan post-hoc test, $p \leq 0.05$).

Some areas concentrated a mean biomass of certain species in particular. The West Archipelago area was characterized by a high mean biomass of *D. dentex* of

983 g.125 m⁻². This was the only area where the species was recorded. The East Mainland area showed mean biomasses of 486 g.125 m⁻² of *S. cretense*, 449 g.125 m⁻² of *D. vulgaris*, and 446 g.125 m⁻² of *O. melanura*. In the East Archipelago we recorded a mean biomass of *S. cretense* of 445 g.125 m⁻². In the West Mainland area, the species with the highest mean biomass was *D. vulgaris* with 283 g.125 m⁻².

Figure 9. Mean total biomass (wet mass in g.125 m⁻²) per site (excluding gregarious species). The whiskers correspond to the standard error (+ S.E.).

Figure 10. Mean total biomass (wet mass in g.125 m⁻²) by area. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (+/- S.E.). The letters illustrate the significance or non-significance of differences between means given by statistical tests; two areas with no letters in common differ significantly from each other for the considered response variable.

4.1.5. Emblematic species (*Epinephelus marginatus* and *Sciaena umbra*)

Overall, few individuals of the emblematic species *E. marginatus* and *S. umbra* were observed (Fig. 11). A total of 14 individuals of *E. marginatus* were observed, with a maximum of 4 in site 26. Concerning *S. umbra*, only 2 individuals of 22 cm were observed at site 45 (Fig. 11, Fig. 12). Overall, the mean total length of *E. marginatus* individuals was relatively low, with a maximum in site 31 where the mean total length of the 2 observed individuals was 46 cm (Fig. 12). In general, these two species did not therefore constitute a significant abundance and biomass at the sites where they were recorded (Fig. 11, Fig. 13) except in site 31 where *E. marginatus* showed a mean biomass of 710 g.125 m⁻².

Figure 11. Total number of emblematic *E. marginatus* and *S. umbra* species per site. Numbers of observed individuals are specified (n).

Figure 12. Mean Total Length (TL in cm) per site of the emblematic species *E. marginatus* and *S. umbra* for sites where at least one of the species was present. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (- S.E.).

Figure 13. Mean biomass ($\text{g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$) per site of the emblematic species *E. marginatus* and *S. umbra*. The whiskers correspond to the standard error ($- \text{S.E.}$).

4.1.6. Commercial species

For a subset of commercial species (*D. annularis*, *D. puntazzo*, *D. sargus*, *D. vulgaris*, *D. dentex*, *C. julis*, *L. merula*, *L. viridis*, *M. surmuletus*, *O. melanura*, *S. scribea*, *S. salpa*, et *S. aurata*), the East Mainland area showed higher mean abundance and biomass of *D. vulgaris*, *D. puntazzo*, *L. merula*, *L. viridis*, *O. melanura* and *S. scribea* (Fig. 14, Fig. 15). However, individuals of these species did not show a greater mean size (Fig. 16). The higher biomass can therefore only be explained by the higher mean abundance of these species in the East Mainland area. Individuals of *D. annularis* and *D. sargus* were on average more abundant and constituted a higher biomass in the West Mainland area (Fig. 14, Fig. 15). Our results did not show any area with a lower fishing pressure of a teleost assemblage targeted by fishing than another area.

Figure 14. Description of the Teleost assemblage targeted by the fishery in terms of mean abundance (ind.125 m⁻²). The whiskers correspond to the standard error (-S.E.).

Figure 15. Description of the Teleost assemblage targeted by the fishery in terms of mean biomass (g.125 m⁻²). The whiskers correspond to the standard error (-S.E.).

Figure 16. Description of the Teleost assemblage targeted by the fishery in terms of mean size (TL: Total Length, in cm). The whiskers correspond to the standard error (-S.E.).

4.2. Comparison with other Mediterranean MPAs

Data from other MPAs studied in the framework of the MPAs Odyssey project and from previous studies (BIOMEX programme, Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008), allow us to put these results into perspective (Tab. 1, Fig. 17).

The Lastovo Islands Nature Park MPA is among those with the lowest teleost mean abundance and mean biomass (Tab. 1, Fig. 17), both in the unprotected area and in potential No-Take Zones. There were no clear differences between the potential NTZ and the unprotected areas of the MPA, either in terms of mean species richness, mean abundance or mean biomass (Tab. 1, Fig. 17), which was not surprising since protection is not yet effective in these potential No-Take Zones.

Tableau 1 : Mean species richness, mean abundance and mean biomass recorded in different Mediterranean MPAs during the BIOMEX (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008) and MPA Odyssey (2021–2023) projects. Increasing gradation of protection: Unprotected < Partially protected < No-Take Zone. NB: within the Dilek Peninsula MPA (Turkey), "partially protected" status prohibits professional fishing and authorizes recreational fishing, while within the Tagomago MPA, "Partially protected" status prohibits spearfishing and imposes limited licence for professional fishing. In all other MPAs, "Partially protected" status prohibits recreational fishing and authorizes professional fishing. In Lastovo Islands Nature Parks (bold characters), the No-Take Zones are not yet effective and are only at the project stage.

Marine Protected Area	Project	Protection type	Mean species richness	Mean abundance (ind.125 m ⁻²)	Mean Biomass (g.125 m ⁻²)
RN Cerbère-Banyuls	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	11.2	79.2	16 300
RN Cerbère-Banyuls	BIOMEX	Unprotected	10.8	70.5	4 000
Cabo de Palos	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	12.9	99.0	28 200
Cabo de Palos	BIOMEX	Unprotected	9.8	60.1	2 900
Cabrera	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	14.1	93.0	13 600
Cabrera	BIOMEX	Unprotected	13.9	71.6	2 700
Carry le Rouet	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	13.1	99.3	16 300
Carry le Rouet	BIOMEX	Unprotected	12.4	64.1	2 400
Medes	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	13.8	61.1	17 500
Medes	BIOMEX	Unprotected	10.2	31.5	2 700
Tabarca	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	12.3	113.6	9 400
Tabarca	BIOMEX	Unprotected	13.3	98.3	5 300
PNMCCA	MPA Odyssey	No-Take Zone	10.4	58.0	2 771
PNMCCA	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	9.7	56.7	1 908
Dilek Peninsula	MPA Odyssey	Reinforced Protection	9.7	106.7	3 909
Dilek Peninsula	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	10.2	100.0	3 720
RN Bouches de Bonifacio	MPA Odyssey	No-Take Zone	11.7	106.2	7 185
RN Bouches de Bonifacio	MPA Odyssey	Partially protected	12.3	118.2	6 654
RN Bouches de Bonifacio	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	10.9	85.6	1 829
PNRC / RN Scandola	MPA Odyssey	Integral Reserve / No-Take Zone	12.3	152.8	14 209
PNRC / RN Scandola	MPA Odyssey	Cantonment / No-Take Zone	11.6	90	3861
PNRC / RN Scandola	MPA Odyssey	Partially protected	11.4	121.0	6 694
PNRC / RN Scandola	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	10.3	76.5	2 398
Tago Mago (Ibiza)	MPA Odyssey	No-Take Zone	10.1	32.8	4673

Tago Mago (Ibiza)	MPA Odyssey	Partially protected	11.6	100	6325
Tago Mago (Ibiza)	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	9.3	70	2316
Lastovo Islands Nature Park	MPA Odyssey	Potential No-Take Zones (but still unprotected)	11.2	74.3	2646
Lastovo Islands Nature Park	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	11.7	77.5	2296

Figure 17. Descriptors (mean biomass and total abundance) of teleost communities in protected and unprotected areas of different MPAs studied in the Mediterranean - Data from 2023 at Lastovo Islands Nature Park (LINP) are presented next to data from the other study areas of the BIOMEX program (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008) and the MPA Odyssey project (2021-2023). Increasing gradation of protection: Unprotected < Partially protected < No-Take Zone (protected). Note: for Lastovo, NTZs are not set-up and remain as a project (still unprotected).

These differences in mean biomass and mean abundance between different MPAs could also be due to natural differences (specific local environmental influences). Comparing abundance and biomass ratios inside/outside the MPA helps to eliminate the influence of these local conditions (Fig. 18). In the absence of partially protected or No-Take zones within the MPA, it is logical that Lastovo Islands Nature Park is among the least effective MPAs studied, with low abundance and low biomass ratios in either unprotected areas and not yet No-Take Zones. However, LINP is comparable to other MPAs such as Cape Corsica, Scandola Cantonnement, Tabarca or Dilek Peninsula, where there are no regulations or actual enforcement to limit the impact of fishing activities (recreational or professional) (Fig. 18). The implementation of effective and efficient No-Take Zones in the

future in LINP would enable the MPA to produce greater biomass and abundance of teleost assemblages. In the next section we calculated what would be the benefits from such scenarios.

Figure 18. Assessment of the effectiveness of the protection implemented in each MPA (points) studied in the BIOMEX and MPA Odyssey projects *via* the ratios inside the zones with protection status (ZNP: No-Take Zones; ZPR: Partially protected zones) *versus* outside the zones with protection status (Outside No-Take Zones) of each MPA, for abundance (x-axis) and biomass (y-axis) respectively. For the Lastovo Islands Nature Park (LINP), the comparison is made between potential No-Take Zones (still unprotected) areas and unprotected areas (see the map Fig. 1 for more details). The dotted lines indicate the average ratio found for a set of representative Mediterranean MPAs (i.e. with ZNPs actually implemented and respected) by the study by Giakoumi et al. (Giakoumi et al., 2017).

5. Discussion

5.1. Robustness of the method

The Underwater Visual Census (UVC) method is a well-tested approach that gives reliable results provided that operators are trained and inter-calibrated, a precaution that was taken here (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 1985). More recent methodological variants exist, for example with a transect width that varies according to the species considered (Prato et al., 2017), but the classic version of the UVCs has been preferred here in order to be able to compare the results with the existing literature on previous studies in Mediterranean MPAs (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008).

It should be remembered here that this method is adapted to the inventory of necto-benthic species only. It is therefore not surprising that we hardly observed crypto-benthic species, such as Scorpaenidae, which are rare in our quantitative data.

One of the difficulties we faced consisted in sampling a constant habitat: the target habitat (infralittoral rocky reefs at a depth of 5 m to 15 m) was not always present, leading us to sometimes consider a mixed habitat of rocky bottoms partially covered by *P. oceanica* meadows (taking care not to exceed 50% cover). This variability in the characteristics of the habitat between our samples inevitably leads to a relative bias, although acceptable, that must be kept in mind.

5.2. General status of the assemblages

On the whole, the surveys of Teleost fish assemblages that we have carried out show the presence of the typical species assemblages of the rocky NW Mediterranean infralittoral, but with areas of relatively low species richness and numbers dominated by small size classes compared with other areas of the NW Mediterranean (Garcia-Rubies and Zabala, 1990). This was particularly true in the West Mainland and East Mainland Areas, where mean abundance and mean biomass were quite low.

Overall, teleost communities appeared richer and showed a generally higher mean abundance and biomass on the Lastovo Islands Nature Park's small islands and isolated archipelagos.

Emblematic species such as *S. umbra* or *E. marginatus* have hardly been recorded throughout the MPA. No invasive exotic species have been identified. Meanwhile, the high presence and abundance of thermophilic species such as *S. cretense* and *T. pavo*, as well as the presence of *S. maderensis*, certainly underscores the general warming of the MPA's waters.

5.3. Assemblages in currently designed potential NTZ and proposition of an alternative scenario

Within sites located in the potential No-Take Zones, the Teleost assemblages sampled did not differ from those sampled overall in the archipelago, either in terms of composition, mean abundance, mean size or mean biomass. There was no greater abundance or biomass of emblematic species (*E. marginatus*, *S. umbra*) in sites located in the potential no-take zones than outside. Among the sites that emerged above the others in terms of mean abundance or biomass, only sites 9, 15 and 19 were located in potential No-Take Zones. Site 15 was the site with the highest mean abundance observed, and this abundance consisted mainly of juveniles of *S. tinca*. Site 19 was the site with the highest biomass observed, mainly consisting of a shoal of 30 individuals of *D. dentex* and the highest biomass of *D. vulgaris* recorded during the mission. With the exception of these observations, the areas identified as potential No-Take Zones did not appear to have teleost assemblages in a better state of conservation than the other sites studied during this mission.

With regard to the size of strong protection areas, previous work in other regions shows that, for a given species, densities are significantly higher within fully protected areas (i.e., No-Take Zones) when these areas are larger than the known home range of that given species (Di Franco et al., 2018). Consequently, this study has highlighted the existence of a direct link between the effectiveness of fully protected areas and species home ranges: Di Franco et al. suggest that fully protected areas of at least **3.6 km²** (360 ha) can increase the density of local populations of these coastal marine species (e.g. *Diplodus* spp.

Serranus spp. *Epinephelus* spp., *S. salpa*). None of the potential No-Take zones planned within the Lastovo Islands Nature Park reaches this threshold.

Given the large size of the Lastovo Archipelago Nature Park (143 km² of sea), it is particularly conceivable to create several No-Take Zones of at least 360 ha. During this mission, we identified several sites where the biocenosis of the infralittoral rocky reefs displayed dense mixed algal forests of *Cystoseira* (*C. foeniculacea*) and *Sargassum* (*S. vulgare*). These habitats provide a particularly favourable nursery environment for juvenile teleost fish (Cheminée et al., 2017, 2013), as observed at site 15 with a high abundance of juvenile *S. tinca*. These sites with remarkable algae forests were often located near a coralligenous drop-off, sometimes reaching depths exceeding 60 m, or a *Posidonia oceanica* meadow. These underwater landscapes appear to be characteristic of isolated islets in the West Archipelago area, as well as sites located south of the main island, spanning the West Mainland and East Mainland areas. These sites, hosting all or part of the Mediterranean landscape mosaic, appear interesting to consider for the establishment of strong protection zones. Protecting them over an area of at least 3.6 km² (360 ha) could benefit the entire MPA but also extend benefits if the protection measures are effective. This type of protection, implemented in a few areas located in isolated island archipelagos and south of the main island, may prove more effective than the planned protection across numerous small areas throughout the entire MPA. The next section presents such scenarios.

6. Management recommendations

6.1. Future protections to be implemented: effective implementation of No-Take Zones, Professional Fishing Reserved Areas surrounding the NTZ and recreational fishing regulations

6.1.1 Introduction of the concept

The LINP has been in place since 2006, but fish communities, and therefore fishermen, do not actually benefit from this status. Fish assemblages are globally poor in specific richness, abundance and biomass, in the range or lower than what can be found in any unprotected rocky area in the Mediterranean. The reason for this poorness is the absence of No Take Zones (NTZ) within the boundaries of the LINP. Such zones should not be taken as “closed” or as “lost fishing ground”, on the contrary, many scientific papers (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008) have demonstrated that they produce extra biomass that is exported and become available for fisheries outside. In Carry Le Rouet (France), it has been demonstrated that one 85 ha NTZ produced 106 tonnes of fish biomass.

In LINP, such NTZ should enhance the biomass available. By surrounding these NTZ with areas where only professional fishing is allowed (Professional Fishing Reserved Areas-PFRA) would ensure that the extra biomass produced is directly benefiting the professional fishermen community. For two examples in Corsica (Natural Reserve of Scandola and Bonifacio) in such areas where fishing is only allowed to professional, the biomass present is 4 and 5 times higher than in open areas with no restriction. In Bonifacio, the catch per unit effort (CPUE) has increased by 60% to 80% (80% for species targeted by spearfishing) for fishermen six years after banning recreational fishing from such areas.

Such modules coupling NTZ surrounded by areas reserved for professional fishing (PFRA) are the core of our recommendations for the LINP. They are the key to combine biodiversity protection, restoration of the halieutic resources, and economical wealth for local fishermen.

Our study allowed us to identify some sites richer than average with teleost assemblages in a better state of conservation than the other sites studied and with remarkable habitats such as macrophyte forests or isolated islets with coralligenous drop-offs (see section 5.4) (e.g., sites 9, 15 and 19).

These sites are examples of good candidates for prioritising the effective implementation of the NTZ plan. The scientific community has shown that strong protection zones with a surface area of at least 3.6 km² are preferable (Di Franco et al., 2018). Even though it is not always easy or possible to create such big NTZs in the context of an archipelago with small islands like LINP, it is essential to consider this and increase the surface area of these potential NTZs with a view to optimising the benefits offered by strong protection.

6.1.2. Creation of No-Take Zones with larger surface areas

The current plan for future No-Take Zones includes 15 potential zones, but none of them covers a surface of 3.6 km². Our results and the scientific literature suggest that it would be preferable to increase the surface area of these NTZs, even if it means reducing their number. Keeping in mind the “SLOSS – Single Large Or Several Small” dilemma for biodiversity conservation, it seems better to imagine management plans with several smaller strong protection zones rather than a single large one (Fahrig et al., 2022 and references inside). However, in our case, few NTZs with a surface area of at least 3.6 km² would certainly bring more benefits than the (too) numerous 15 (very small) ones with a surface of approximately 3.6 km². Given the large size of the Lastovo Islands Nature Park (143 km²), it seems possible to draw up a conservation plan based on several No-Take Zones of approximately 3.6 km². However, given the spatial constraints, which mean that 3.6 km² (360 ha) NTZs surrounded by PFRAs are not systematically imaginable, it would seem acceptable to reduce this area for future NTZs (Fig. 19).

6.1.3. Creation of zones reserved for small-scale professional fishing (PFRAs)

Our previous work has shown (particularly in the Scandola Nature Reserve – Corsica; Estaque et al, 2023) that partially protected zones reserved for professional fishing provide good benefits, sometimes comparable to those provided by a No Take-Zone. Integrated within the Lastovo Islands Nature Park, this type of Professional Fishing Reserved Areas should be considered as a complement to NTZs. Ideally, NTZs should be surrounded by such zones (Fig. 19). In general, these zones reserved for professional fishermen allow them to be considered in the decision-making, encourage them to take part into the management and to increase the conservation effort by agreeing to the NTZs.

Figure 19. Map showing the implementation scenario for No-Take Zones (red polygons) surrounded by zones reserved for small-scale professional fishing (PFRA, orange polygon) within the Lastovo Islands Nature Park. Given the size of the archipelago, not all areas measure 360 ha.

Based on our scenario calculations (Tab. 2), the implementation of No-Take Zones surrounded by zones reserved for professional fishermen would allow fish production to be on average 173% higher than at the present state (reaching from 607 t.year⁻¹ to 1,118 t.year⁻¹): indeed, in our scenarios, the increase in production varied according to the zones, from 145% to 188%, and seemed particularly significant for the Lukovici and Glavat zones, where the increase in production will be 187% and 188% respectively (Tab. 2). This production will constitute a stock directly available in the zones specially reserved for small scale professional fishing (PFRA, Fig. 19).

To summarize: by creating only NTZs, the loss of fishing ground will be about 100% compensated by the extra biomass produced and exported by the NTZs. If PFRAs are added around or in the vicinity of these NTZs, the benefits in biomass catchable for local artisanal fishermen would be from 145% to 200%.

Tableau 2 : Zones (as referred to in Fig. 19) and Total production in tons per year. Current production, different scenario productions and production increase (%) are presented for each different zone and for the total. The first scenario corresponds to the **potential production** increased by the exedentary production resulting from the setting up of the **NTZ** (i.e. production available around the NTZ once protected *versus* production available when not protected), while the rest of the zone remains open to all types of fishing. The second scenario corresponds to the **potential production** increased by the two exedentary productions resulting (a) from the setting up of the **NTZ** and (b) resulting from the setting up of the surrounding **PFRA**.

Zones	Surface NTZ/PFRA	Current Production (t.year ⁻¹)	Scenario 1 - Potential Production NTZ (t.year ⁻¹)	Scenario 2 - Potential Production NTZ + PFRA (t.year ⁻¹)	Global production increase
Lukovici	20,8%	145	144	271	187%
Glavat	19,6%	63	62	117	188%
Bijelac	-	244	-	488	200%
Struga	33,4%	49	48	75	153%
Skoj od Mrcare	25,9%	59	59	98	166%
Otok Susac	79,8%	48	48	70	145%
TOTAL	-	607	605	1,118	173%

6.1.4. Regulation of recreational fishing

Recreational fishing extracts biomass from coastal environments on a scale comparable to professional fishing, which is not sustainable. The consideration of implementing quotas and minimum size limits for recreational fishing and spearfishing, to be determined by the managers of the Lastovo Islands Nature Park, across the entirety of the MPA area should be taken into account.

6.1.5. Reinforced patrolling

In order for the various protection levels to fully fulfil their roles and complement each other, it is essential to enhance surveillance, particularly in the zoning of the future No-Take Zones and Professional Fishing Reserved Areas.

6.3. Essential habitats protection

The management of fishing activities (No-Take Zones, PFRA, etc.) ensures the maintenance of adult populations with sizes and abundances allowing for reproduction. To complete the life cycle of species and guarantee population renewal, another crucial step must be preserved: the settlement and growth of juveniles within coastal habitats acting as nurseries (Cheminée et al., 2014). Management measures should thus include the protection of nursery habitats themselves to prevent their loss or transformation, which would compromise their function (Cheminée et al., 2017). In coastal zones, various habitats in the infralittoral mosaic and their interfaces play this role and should benefit from strong protective measures (Cheminée et al., 2021).

At least three habitats in the depth range of 0–15 meters are particularly concerned: marine forests covering infralittoral rocks (Sargassaceae, Fucales, Phaeophyceae, such as forests of the genus *Cystoseira sensu lato*), heterogeneous shallow rocky bottoms (HSR, i.e. : blocks and gravel on very shallow gentle slopes), and *Posidonia oceanica* meadows. To preserve these habitats, protective measures do not directly target fishing but rather other human activities:

- For seagrass meadows, impacts from ship anchoring can be limited through mooring management.
- For heterogeneous shallow bottoms (HSR): located at the bottom of bays and coves, this habitat is vulnerable to changes in the coastline, developments with bottom reshaping, etc.
- Regarding *Cystoseira* and *Sargassum* forests, the canopy formed by these arborescent macrophytes is sensitive to various direct and indirect anthropogenic pressures: indirect pressures include overfishing relieving herbivorous organisms (sea urchins) from fish predation pressure (*Sparus aurata*, *Diplodus* spp., etc.), leading to their proliferation and overgrazing of forests. Directly, this habitat can also be degraded by anchorages. The management of anchorages should be strengthened. Anchorages can also be reduced through the expansion of areas under partial protection (PFRA), which will limit the presence of recreational fishing vessels by default.

6.4. Future monitorings

The methodology implemented in this study has enabled the assessment of Teleost assemblages that could serve as a future reference, especially in areas that have not been previously monitored. If management measures with strong protections were established in these areas, it would be advisable to conduct regular inventories over time to monitor the status of assemblages and observe the anticipated emergence of a "reserve effect."

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8. Appendix

Appendix A1 : Site names, identification number and localisation				
Name	Number	Latitude	Longitude	Date
Glavat	1	42,76571	17,14422	01/10/2023
Golubinjak	2	42,76568	16,99545	25/09/2023
Golubinjak	3	42,76482	16,98955	25/09/2023
Petrovac	4	42,75767	16,95944	26/09/2023
Petrovac	5	42,75467	16,95113	25/09/2023
Lukovici	6	42,77516	16,9474	25/09/2023
Lukovici	7	42,77415	16,95252	25/09/2023
Struga	8	42,72682	16,89489	26/09/2023
Struga	9	42,72464	16,88972	26/09/2023
Zona od Mrtca	10	42,73209	16,85653	26/09/2023
Zona od Mrtca	11	42,72995	16,84625	26/09/2023
Bratin	12	42,74553	16,80101	27/09/2023
Tovari	13	42,77614	16,82265	27/09/2023
Tovari	14	42,77903	16,82616	27/09/2023
Skoj od Mrcare	15	42,78081	16,77579	27/09/2023
Skoj od Kopist	16	42,76265	16,72516	29/09/2023

Kopist	17	42,74843	16,72427	27/09/2023
Kopist	18	42,74871	16,71151	27/09/2023
Bijelac	19	42,7591	16,67941	28/09/2023
Otok Susac Sud	20	42,75402	16,49778	28/09/2023
Otok Susac Sud	21	42,75158	16,49446	28/09/2023
Otok Susac	22	42,76026	16,4937	28/09/2023
Otok Susac	23	42,76398	16,49954	28/09/2023
Otok Susac	24	42,77001	16,5291	28/09/2023
Otok Susac Sud	25	42,76165	16,51198	28/09/2023
Kopist	26	42,75903	16,7252	28/09/2023
Kopist	27	42,751	16,73179	29/09/2023
Otok Mrčara	28	42,77226	16,79705	27/09/2023
Otok Mrčara	29	42,76008	16,79332	27/09/2023
Pasadur	30	42,7538	16,81181	27/09/2023
Uvala Danja Planka	31	42,74298	16,81664	27/09/2023
Skrivena Luka Bay	34	42,73116	16,86528	26/09/2023
Otočić Uska	35	42,73202	16,87549	26/09/2023
Duboke	37	42,75184	16,93663	26/09/2023
Novi Hum	38	42,76658	16,94351	25/09/2023

Uvala Zace	39	42,77528	16,93302	30/09/2023
Zaklopatica	40	42,77673	16,8797	30/09/2023
Stomorina	41	42,77418	16,96809	25/09/2023
Krucica	42	42,76262	16,96966	25/09/2023
Krucica	43	42,76099	16,96226	25/09/2023
Saplun	45	42,77932	16,99558	30/09/2023
Arženjak veli	46	42,78328	16,99247	25/09/2023
Mrkljenta Bijela	47	42,78212	17,01471	30/09/2023
Mrkljenta Crna	48	42,797171	16,99629	30/09/2023
Veli Tajan	49	42,81608	16,98868	30/09/2023
Gornja Sestrica	50	42,75862	17,07437	30/09/2023
Danji Vlačnik	51	42,760076	17,103437	30/09/2023
Otočić Gornji Vlačnik	52	42,76349	17,11521	30/09/2023
Otočić Gornji Vlačnik	53	42,46434	17,12288	30/09/2023
Glavat	54	42,76943	17,13806	01/10/2023
Banci	55	42,76338	17,0808	01/10/2023

Appendix A2 : List of observed species, classified by family. English common names are given for each species. Species commonly targeted by fishing are highlighted in grey.

Family	Species Sampled	Common name (English)
Labridae	<i>Coris julis</i> <i>Thalassoma pavo</i> <i>Labrus viridis</i> <i>Labrus merula</i> <i>Labrus mixtus</i> <i>Symphodus ocellatus</i> <i>Symphodus cinereus</i> <i>Symphodus mediterraneus</i> <i>Symphodus tinca</i> <i>Symphodus roissali</i> <i>Symphodus doderleini</i> <i>Symphodus rostratus</i> <i>Centrolabrus melanocercus</i>	Mediterranean rainbow wrasse Ornate wrasse Green wrasse Brown wrasse Cuckoo wrasse Ocellated wrasse Grey wrasse Axillary wrasse East Atlantic peacock wrasse Five-spotted wrasse NA Sublet Black-tailed wrasse
Sparidae	<i>Dentex dentex</i> <i>Diplodus annularis</i> <i>Diplodus vulgaris</i> <i>Diplodus puntazzo</i> <i>Diplodus sargus</i> <i>Spondylisoma cantharus</i> <i>Oblada melanura</i> <i>Sarpa salpa</i> <i>Sparisoma cretense</i> <i>Sparus aurata</i> <i>Boops boops</i> <i>Spicara sp.</i>	Common dentex Annular seabream Common two-banded seabream Sharpsnout seabream White seabream Black seabream Saddled seabream Salema Parrotfish Gilthead seabream Bogue Picarel
Carangidae	<i>Seriola dumerili</i>	Greater amberjack
Pomacentridae	<i>Chromis chromis</i>	Damselfish
Phycidae	<i>Phycis phycis</i>	Forkbeard
Epinephelidae	<i>Epinephelus marginatus</i>	Dusky grouper
Apogonidae	<i>Apogon imberbis</i>	Cardinal fish
Serranidae	<i>Serranus scriba</i> <i>Serranus cabrilla</i>	<i>Painted comber</i> <i>Comber</i>
Sphyraenidae	<i>Sphyraena viridensis</i>	Yellowmouth barracuda

Scorpaenidae	<i>Scorpaena notata</i> <i>Scorpaena porcus</i> <i>Scorpaena scrofa</i> <i>Scorpaena maderensis</i>	Small red scorpionfish Black scorpionfish Red scorpionfish Madeira rockfish
Mullidae	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	Surmullet
Muraenidae	<i>Muraena helena</i>	Mediterranean moray
Sciaenidae	<i>Sciaena umbra</i>	Brown meagre